

HERPETIC STOMATITIS TREATMENT IN CHILDREN.

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Abstract. Herpetic stomatitis is a viral infection of the mouth that causes sores and ulcers. These mouth ulcers are not the same as canker sores, which are not caused by a virus. Abnormally enlarged, bulging, protruding, or swollen gums are a possible indication of disease.

Key words: herpetic stomatitis, virus, mouth, sores, ulcers, infection, gums.

ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ГЕРПЕТИЧЕСКОГО СТОМАТИТА У ДЕТЕЙ.

Аннотация. Герпетический стоматит – это вирусная инфекция, которая вызывает язвы и воспаление во рту. Эти язвы полости рта отличаются от язв, которые не вызваны вирусом. Аномально увеличенные выпуклые и опухшие десны являются возможным признаком заболевания.

Ключевые слова: герпетический стоматит, язва, вирус, ротовая полость, инфекция, десны.

Herpes stomatitis is a viral infection which causes ulcers and inflammation in the mouth. These mouth ulcers are different from canker sores, which are not caused by a virus. Herpes stomatitis is caused by the HSV (Herpes Simplex Virus) and it is most common in young children, usually between the ages of six months to five years. It is a highly contagious disease. You child can become infected with herpes stomatitis if you or another adult in the family suffer from cold sores, which are fluid-filled sores occurring on or around the lips. However, most often the exact reason for herpes stomatitis is not known.

The causative agent is Herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1), which belongs to the alphaherpesvirus group. The virus is enveloped and has a linear double-stranded DNA genome. HSV-1 is mostly responsible for oral, ocular, and facial infections as it has a tropism for oral epithelium. While most cases of herpetic gingivostomatitis are associated with HSV-1 infection, some adult cases have been reported where HSV-2 was isolated from the oral lesions. Oral infection with HSV-2 is probably transmitted through orogenital contact and has also been observed in HIV-positive patients and patients undergoing immunosuppressive therapy.[3]

Symptoms may include: blisters in the mouth, often on the tongue, cheeks, roof of the mouth, gums, and on the border between the inside of the lip and the skin next to it, after blisters pop, they form ulcers in the mouth, often on the tongue or cheeks, difficulty swallowing, drooling, fever, often as high as 104°F (40°C), which may occur 1 to 2 days before blisters and ulcers appear, irritability, mouth pain, swollen gums. Symptoms may be so uncomfortable that your child doesn't want to eat or drink. Your doctor will be able to offer a diagnoses based on the visual exam of the mouth sores. But for confirmation, your doctor may request special laboratory tests of the mouth sores.

Currently, eight types of herpes viruses were isolated, which are wide spread among the population worldwide [1]. Clinical signs of most herpetic infections may be polymorphous, which is associated with the impairment of various organs and systems [2]. Isolation of the DNA of most herpes viruses in the saliva is relevant both for epidemiology (saliva is a vector for the pathogen

transmission) and dentistry [3]. One of the most common conditions in dentistry is herpetic stomatitis, caused by the herpes simplex virus type 1. Therefore, application of the effective treatment methods is not only therapeutic measure, but an important link in the prevention of herpetic infection both in patients (reduction of the number of relapses and increase in remission duration) and in medical staff (reduction of viral burden in patient's saliva ensures low risk of disease transmission during dental procedures) [4].

Study purpose is the assessment of the therapeutic and preventive effect of the complex treatment of chronic herpetic stomatitis caused by herpes simplex virus type 1.

The study included 100 patients with chronic herpetic stomatitis with 3 or more relapses per year, men and women aged from 26 to 70 years. Depending on the conducted treatment, all patients were divided into two groups, matched by gender and age (table 1). Study duration: 2015–2018.

Each group was further divided into three subgroups depending on the severity of the clinical course of the disease:

- Subgroup I — mild degree;
- Subgroup II — moderate degree;
- Subgroup III — severe degree.

The etiology of the disease was determined by polymerase chain reaction studies of scrapes from the affected areas of the oral mucosa, as well as patients' blood. Herpes simplex virus type 1 was identified in all examined patients.

Before herpetic stomatitis treatment, hygienic measures were performed such as professional oral hygiene, treatment of teeth with decay, grinding of sharp tooth edges and fillings on teeth, correction of removable dentures in the oral cavity.

Treatment:

Acyclovir, a medicine your child takes that fights the virus causing the infection, numbing medicine (viscous lidocaine), which you can apply to your child's mouth to ease severe pain, use lidocaine with care, because it can numb all feeling in your child's mouth. This can make it hard for your child to swallow, and may lead to burns in the mouth or throat from eating hot foods, or cause choking.

There are several things you can do at home to help your child feel better: give your child cool, noncarbonated, nonacidic drinks, such as water, milk shakes, or diluted apple juice. Dehydration can occur quickly in children, so make sure your child is getting enough fluids. Offer cool, bland, easy-to-swallow foods such as frozen pops, ice cream, mashed potatoes, gelatin, or applesauce. Give your child acetaminophen or ibuprofen for pain. (Never give aspirin to a child under age 2. It can cause Reye syndrome, a rare, but serious illness.) Bad breath and a coated tongue are common side effects. Gently brush your child's teeth every day. Make sure your child gets plenty of sleep and rests as much as possible. Your child should recover completely within 10 days without treatment. Acyclovir may speed up your child's recovery. Your child will have the herpes virus for life. In most people, the virus stays inactive in their body. If the virus wakes up again, it most often causes a cold sore on the mouth. Sometimes, it can affect the inside of the mouth, but it won't be as severe as the first episode.

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